

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Adherence to pedagogical conditions is important in increasing the effectiveness of teaching programming languages in the continuing education system. Correctly selected and systematically implemented pedagogical conditions allow to achieve high results in practical activities conducted with teachers-students at different levels of education [1].

Therefore, in order to increase the effectiveness of teaching programming languages in the continuing education system, it is necessary to first reveal the meaning of the concept of "pedagogical conditions" and determine its functions in programming languages based on the analysis of scientific literature.

In this regard, i.e. researches related to the concept of pedagogical conditions B.V. Kupriyanov, S.A. Dynina, N. It was studied by such scientists as G. Bajenova, I.V. Khludeeva, A.Kh. Khushbakhtov, S.N. Pavlov, N.V. Ippolitova, M.I. Shalin, O.V. Galkina, O.V. Galkina. They say that the concept of pedagogical conditions is multifaceted, so it has many interpretations. The ambiguity of the concept is determined by several approaches to its understanding. The following can be described as a condition: 1) the environment in which something happens; 2) a situation in which something depends; 3) regulations introduced in a specific field of activity. Thus, the concept of a condition interacts with the subject, implying the events that surround him, without which he cannot imagine [2, 3].

A set of specific conditions forms the environment for its emergence, existence and development. A.Kh. Khushbakhtov, S.N. Pavlov, N.V. Ippolitova analyze the concept of condition. As a result, the researchers come to the conclusion that the concept of condition has a universal character, and its essence in pedagogy can be described as the relationship of causes and circumstances. Here it is important to understand that the relationship of causes and conditions directly affects the development, upbringing and education of a person, as well as the final results of these processes.

V. Kupriyanov, S.A. Dynina, N.G. Bajenova, I.V. Khludeeva generalize and identify different groups of conditions. As noted, objective and subjective conditions according to the nature of the effect, general and specific conditions according to the specific characteristics of the object of influence. The authors

recommend the use of groups of conditions organized according to certain characteristics in the analysis of specific pedagogical situations.

Thus, pedagogical conditions are a set of specially based and organized conditions and directions of pedagogical activity that determine the effectiveness of the educational process, at various stages, and in general, the achievement of the result of the educational process [2, 3].

Based on this given definition, the following pedagogical conditions should be followed in order to increase the effectiveness of teaching programming languages in the continuous education system and to increase the motivation and creative ability of students in programming, as well as in the formation and development of their competencies:

- improving students' mathematical literacy;
- formation and development of students' logical thinking;
- to increase the creative ability of students-students regarding algorithmization, to form and develop their competencies;
- forming and developing the ability to transfer the given algorithm to the program code;
- to teach students how to generate a problem condition from the given program code;
- to increase students' culture, interest and creative ability to work in the environment of visual and object-oriented programming languages, to develop cognitive thinking;
- teaching students to prepare practical projects using visual and object-oriented programming languages;
- formation and development of the culture of collective implementation of given practical projects.

By following such pedagogical conditions, it is possible to increase students' motivation for programming languages, develop their creative thinking, and develop their competence. Therefore, today it is necessary to develop new approaches to increase the effectiveness of teaching programming languages. In the implementation of these, the use of advanced pedagogical technologies and modern didactic digital technologies and problem assignments is considered appropriate.

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